

Software Testing Strategies and Techniques

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Abstract: This paper discusses different software strategies such as unit testing, integration testing, validation testing and techniques such as white box and black box testing for conventional and object oriented software development. Strategy provides a guideline to conduct testing. The testing carried out at different stages in software development life cycle is described by the various testing methods.

Keywords: Test cases, integration, cyclomatic complexity, security testing, performance testing, stress testing, recovery testing.

I. INTRODUCTION

A process of executing a program with the goal of finding errors is Software Testing. A Software Testing Strategy helps to convert test case designs into a well-planned execution steps that will result in the construction of successful software. Software testing aims at uncovering the errors in software. So the primary goal of test cases is to derive set of tests that have highest probability of uncovering the errors. Software testing is a series of process which is designed to make sure that the computer code does what it was designed to do. Software testing is a destructive process of trying to find the errors. The main purpose of testing can be quality assurance, reliability estimation, validation or verification.

II. SOFTWARE TESTING STRATEGY

Testing is the set of activities that can be planned in advance and conducted systematically. To define these activities templates are provided by different testing strategies. All the strategies have following characteristics:

1. A software team should conduct effective formal reviews. This eliminates many errors before testing starts.

2. Testing begins at component level and works "outward" towards the integration of entire computer based system.
3. Different testing techniques are appropriate at different points in time.
4. Testing is conducted by the developer and for large project, an independent test group.
5. Testing and debugging are different activities, but debugging must be included in any testing strategy.

For large projects independent test group (ITG) is hired to remove conflict of interest that may be present if software is been tested by developers only. This is because ITG is paid to find errors.

1.1 Strategy for conventional software Architecture

Conventional software development is a spiral process. The testing may also be viewed in context of spiral.

2.1.1 Unit testing:

At vertex of spiral, testing begins with unit testing. It aims at testing each component or unit of software to check its functionality, independently. Ensures that it works properly as a unit. Typical units are

- Interface: tested to check proper flow of information into and out of the program unit under test.
- Local data structures: tested to check integrity of data during execution.
- Boundary conditions: tested to ensure unit operates properly at boundaries to limit processing.
- Independent paths: tested to ensure all statements in the unit are executed at least once.
- Error handling paths: tested to check whether error messages are user friendly and corresponds to error encountered, whether they reroute or terminate process when error occurred.
- Common errors found during unit testing are: incorrect initialization, precision inaccuracy, mixed mode operation, incorrect arithmetic precedence etc.

2.1.2 Integration testing: Further progressing the testing process, these units must be assembled or integrated to form complete software package. So integration testing focuses the problems of verification and construction.

2.1.3 Validation testing: Taking one more outward turn along spiral, comes validation testing. It consists of higher order tests using validation criteria defined during requirement analysis phase. This test assures that software meets all functional, behavioral and performance requirements.

1.2 Strategy for object oriented Architecture

Strategy for object oriented Architecture are:

2.2.1 Unit testing in Object oriented context

Concept of unit testing in OO context differs from conventional approach. Operation is the smallest unit of testing. As here operation may be inherited, it will have different context in different classes. So unit testing for OO software is driven by operations encapsulated by the class and state behavior of the class.

2.2.2 Integration testing Object oriented context

Three approaches used are:

- **Thread based testing-** threads are sets of classes in OO approach. All the classes responding to one input or event form a set. Each thread is tested individually.
- **User based testing-** focuses on independent classes. These classes don't collaborate with other classes. Then dependent classes, those which use independent classes, are tested.
- **Cluster testing-** collaborating classes form a cluster, this testing is used to uncover errors in the collaboration.

2.2.3 Validation Testing: It follows the integration testing. At this level testing procedures are same in conventional as well as OO approach. It focuses on user visible actions and user recognizable output from the system, so that software functions in the way required by customer. All the requirements of the customer are specified in a document called as software requirement specification (SRS).

This testing uses SRS's validation criteria section for reference. This testing also includes alpha and beta tests. Both are performed by users. The reason is developers can never predict or know how user will be really using the software. Alpha testing is done at developer's place by end-user while beta testing is done by user at user-site.

Figure 1: Software Testing Strategies

III. SYSTEM TESTING

System comprises of hardware, people, information and software is only the one component of it. It includes recovery testing, security testing, stress testing and performance testing. To test fault tolerance of system, recovery testing fails the software using several inputs and verifies that recovery is performed properly. Security testing verifies the protection mechanism built into system. For this tester will play the role of intruder or hacker and will try to find a key to system entry. In this regard designer of system should design a system in such a way that hacking should be costlier than information obtained from it. Stress testing will check how the system works under abnormal conditions. Abnormal conditions will include generating more interrupts than average rate, increased input data rate, giving input with maximum memory or resources requirements etc.

A variation of stress testing called sensitivity testing identifies the data combinations within valid input classes that can cause improper processing. After performing all above tests finally performance test is conducted to check run time performance of software within the context of an integrated system.

Figure 2: General classification of tests techniques

IV. SOFTWARE TESTING METHODOLOGIES

To accomplish the goal of finding errors two methodologies are used in conventional as well as object oriented approach: white box testing and black box testing.

White box tests focus on control structure in program, to verify all the statements in program are executed at least once as well as all logical conditions are exercised. It includes basis path testing, condition and data flow testing, program logic and loop testing.

Unlike white box testing Black box testing does not require knowledge of program internal working. Testing is carried out to verify functional requirements. It includes equivalent partitioning, boundary value analysis, fault based testing, random testing, partition testing, cause effect graphic technique.

4.1 White Box Testing

Method is also called as glass box testing. Includes the test cases that guarantee that

- 1) Independent paths within a module have been exercised at least once.
- 2) All logical decisions are tested for their both sides, true and false.
- 3) All loops are tested at their boundaries and within their operational bounds.
- 4) Internal data structures are ensured for their validity.

4.1.1 Basic Path Testing: test cases are designed to satisfy goal 1) as listed above. The different techniques used in these tests are:

1. Flow graph notation: Main components of that graphs are:

- *Node* – it represents one or more procedural statements. Node which contains a condition is called *predicate node*.
- *Edges* between nodes – represent flow of control. Each node must be bounded by at least one edge, even if it does not contain any useful information.
- *Region* – an area bounded by nodes and edges.

Figure 3: Different versions of Flow Graph Notation

2. Independent Paths:

The path which includes at least one new set of processing statement or new condition is said to be a independent path. For flow graph, it moves along at least one edge that has not been traversed before the path is defined. For figure 6 independent paths are :

Path 1: 1-2-4-7-8

Path 2: 1-2-3-5-7-8

Path 3: 1-2-3-6-7-8

These paths from 1 to 3 form basis set for Basic path testing. Now test cases are designed to force execution of each at least once.

How many paths to look for is decided by a software metric called cyclomatic complexity. The value evaluated for cyclomatic complexity defines the number of independent paths in the basis set of a program. For the given graph G, cyclomatic complexity V (G) is equal to:

1. The number of regions in the flow graph.
2. $V(G) = E - N + 2$, where E is the number of edges, and N is the number of nodes.
3. $V(G) = P + 1$, where P is the number of predicate nodes.

The core of this technique is: one draws the flow graph according to the design or code, one determines its cyclomatic complexity; cyclomatic complexity can be determined without a flow graph in that case one computes the number of conditional statements in the code after that, one determines a basis set of the linearly independent paths; the predicate nodes are useful when necessary paths must be determined at the end, one prepares test cases by which each path in the basis set will be executed. Each test case will be executed and compared to the expected results.

Figure 4: Flow graph

Cyclomatic complexity for flow graph which is represented in Figure 4 is:

$$V(G) = E - N + 2 = 17 - 13 + 2 = 6.$$

So, the basis set of independent paths is:

Path 1:1-2-10-11-13

Path 2:1-2-10-12-13

Path 3:1-2-3-10-11-13

Path 4:1-2-3-4-5-8-9-2

Path 5:1-2-3-4-5-6-8-9-2

Path 6:1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9-2.

4.1.2 Control Structure Testing: test cases are designed to satisfy goal 2) and 3) as listed above. The different techniques used in these tests are:

- Condition Testing: tests all logical conditions in program.
- Data Flow Testing : test cases are selected as per locations of definitions and uses of variables in the program

4.1.3 Loop Testing: focuses on validity of loop constructs. There are four types of loops:

- a. Simple loops
 - b. Concatenated loops
 - c. Nested loops
 - d. Unstructured loops
- a. Simple loops**

It is possible to execute the following tests:

1. Skip the loop entirely
2. Only one pass through the loop
3. Two passes through the loop
4. m passes through the loop where $m < n$
5. $N-1, N, N+1$ passes through the loop, where n is the maximum number of allowable passes through the loop. A typical simple loop is depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Simple Loop

b. Nested Loops

If one uses this type of loops, it can be possible that the number of probable tests increases as the level of nesting grows. So, one can have an impractical number of tests. To correct this, it is recommended to use the following approach:

1. Start at the innermost loop, and set all other loops to minimum values.
2. Conduct simple loop tests for the innermost loop and holding the outer loop at their minimum iteration parameter value.

3. Work outward, performing tests for the next loop.
4. Continue until all loops have been tested. A typical nested loop is depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Nested Loop

c. Concatenated Loops

These loops are tested using simple loop tests if each loop is independent from the other. Otherwise, nested loops tests are used. A typical concatenated loop is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Concatenated Loop

d. Unstructured Loops

This type of loop should be redesigned. A typical unstructured loop is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Unstructured Loops

4.2 Black Box Testing

Method is also called as behavior testing. Finds errors of types Incorrect or missing function, Interface error, Errors in data structures or external database access, behavior or performance of error, initialization and termination errors. White box testing is performed before Black box testing.

4.2.1 Equivalent Partitioning

Divided program input domain into classes of data that consist of set of valid or invalid states for input conditions. Input condition takes the form of one among numeric value, a set of related values, a range of values or a Boolean condition.

4.2.2 Boundary Value Analysis

Most of the errors occur at the boundary values than center. So this analysis is one of testing method. Test cases verify program execution at each boundary value and are derived from output domain also.

4.2.3 Cause-Effect Graphing Techniques

Used when one wants to translate a policy or procedure specified in a natural language into software's language.

Input conditions and actions are listed for a module, an identifier is allocated for each one of them, cause-effect graph is created, this graph is changed into a decision table, and the rules of this table are modified to test cases.

V. CONCLUSION

Software testing strategies and techniques is an important for improvement and measurement of a software and software development life cycle. It represents the review of specification, design and coding. Software testing also provides an objective, independent view of software to allow the business to appreciate and understand the risk at implementation of software. Various types of software strategies used for conventional and object oriented software development.

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